

FACTORS EFFECTING INVESTMENT DECISION MAKING BEHAVIOR WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SELECTED METROPOLITAN CITIES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the factors that influence investment decision-making behavior through the mediating role of information search. Two factors, overconfidence and economic expectations, are used as independent variables, and investment decision-making behavior is used as the dependent variable. Information search is used as a mediating variable. For this purpose, a survey questionnaire was used to test the hypotheses. The target audience for this study was investors in Pakistan's Lahore Stock Exchange and Faisalabad Exchange. A total of 270 questionnaires were distributed. Of these, only 245 were returned and 11 were not included in the analysis due to incomplete information. Therefore, 229 questionnaires were used in the analysis. Simple regression analysis and multiple regression analysis were used as statistical tools. The results showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between economic expectations and investment decision behavior, but when information seeking is included as a mediator, the relationship becomes insignificant and becomes negative. In case of financial expectations, we offer full mediation. Overconfidence tendencies were also found to be positively and significantly related to investment decision behavior. This trend remained significant even when information seeking was added as a mediator. Suggestion of partial mediation in case of overconfidence.

Keywords: Information searches, decision making behavior

INTRODUCTION

Investing means putting money into any business to generate additional income. For many people, the ability to participate in decision-making through investing seems appealing. By analyzing these results, individuals can practice decision making and thereby assess their ability to make correct decisions. Traditional financial theory assumes that investment markets and their members are rational, pragmatic, and interested in maximizing wealth. However, many factors such as emotions, past experiences, and beliefs often influence investment decisions, leading investors to take unexpected, illogical, and unwise actions. A new field of finance has emerged to understand the influence of these factors on investor decisions. This new field of finance is known as "behavioral finance," and it combines this behavioral approach with traditional financial and economic theory to try to explain the reasons for irrationality in the investment decisions of today's investors. Behavioral finance addresses the internal and external behavioral factors that influence investors' financial decisions. This study discusses the influence of various factors on investment behavior as it relates to behavioral finance. Behavioral finance is a recently emerging field in finance that reveals the influence of various psychological biases not only on observed market outcomes but also on the attitudes of individuals and managers involved in investment decisions.

Accumulation of buyers and sellers of shares (also called stocks) is known as share market which comprises securities listed on a stock exchange and those only traded privately (Akhter and Sangmi, 2015). Share market is an authentic barometer to assess the country's economic condition (Thomsett, 2017). Share market also channelizes a constitutional function in a financial system of the country as it extends charismatic possibilities of investment in diverse securities through which investors can save (Dalton, 1993; Gribnikov and Shevchenko, 2012; Leng and Noronha, 2013; Madura, 2014). Nevertheless, share market is one of the most significant means for organizations to raise money (Knetter, 1994; Rude, 2003).

Statement of the Problem

Previous studies have shown that moderate investor awareness can be a barrier when making investment decisions (Biktimirov and Xu, 2019; Clemons, 2010; Massironi and Guicciardi, 2011; Shah, Ahmad and Mahmood, 2018). In proper financial markets, social, economic, or psychological factors play a role because investment information sources reflect investment intentions, no matter how mysteriously influential other factors may be. You shouldn't. However, if there is a taxonomic bias in the way investors understand information sources, social factors (Hebb, Hamilton, Hachigian, 2010), economic factors (Jayathilake, 2015), or psychological factors (Sarwar and Afaf , 2016) may play a role. Recently, researchers have observed how much exploitation has become in investment decisions. However, investment intentions and antecedents of investment decisions are generally outside the focus of researchers (Andrews, 1978; Rodgers and McFarlin, 2016; Zhu, 2017). Additionally, a few researchers have emphasized the role of financial ability in determining investment decisions. However, it is also unclear whether financial literacy influences investment intentions towards better investment decisions (Abubakar, 2015; Al-Tamimi&Kalli, 2009; Hidajat, 2018).

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this paper is to measure the influence of information sources on individual investors' perceptions of the stock market. This study also investigates the role of individual investors' awareness in determining their investment intentions in the stock market. Investors choose classifiable options that have surprising and different outcomes in life (van Raaij, 2016). Financial theory indicates that such decisions are complex and require a multi-step decision-making process (Ackert and Deaves, 2009; Baker and Wurgler, 2013; Shah, Ahmad and Mahmood, 2018). Therefore, this study evaluates the influence of psychological, social, and economic factors

on stock market investment intentions. Since financial literacy is a fundamental element in measuring investment behavior, this study also investigates the mediating effect of financial literacy from investment intention to investment decision in the stock market.

Objectives

Following objectives are listed in order to answer the above determined research questions:

1. To assess the influence of information source on individual investor awareness regarding share market.
2. To evaluate the role of individual investor awareness in ascertaining share market investment intention.
3. To determine the impact of psychological, social, and economic factors towards share market investment intention.
4. To measure the mediating effects of financial literacy on investment intention towards share market investment decision.
5. To ascertain the association of demographic factors and investment pattern towards individual investor awareness and share market investment intention.
6. To examine the association of demographic factors and investment pattern towards share market investment decision.

Scope of the Study

The basic objective of this study is to develop a research framework to determine the influence of psychological, social, and economic factors on investment intentions in the stock market (Chang, 2014; Kim, Hwang & Hon, 2014; Paul, 1990; Pierce & Geyer, 1991. Scott and Eisner, 1980. Shim, Lee, & Kim, 2008). On a positive note, the development of such a conceptual framework will help capture individuals' investment intentions. This paper contributes to the current

body of knowledge on financial behavior by demonstrating the important relationship between investment intentions and financial literacy (Aren and Aydemir, 2015; Narula, 2017; Ngek, 2016) . This paper can be considered a new study by him in two respects. First, this study suggests a relatively integrated framework that includes psychological, social, and economic factors and an objective source of information for understanding individuals' investment intentions. Second, we measure the mediating effect of financial literacy on investment decisions in the stock market. This can certainly help understand the impact of financial literacy on investment decisions. More importantly, from a researcher's perspective, there is no study that analyzes the mediating effect of financial literacy on investment intentions in stock market investment decisions. Finally, this study contributes to the existing literature by hypothesizing the relationships between these selected attributes.

Operational Definitions

Information Sources

Information sources are the diverse means by which an investor receives information prior to making an investment decision.

Investor Awareness

In investor relations, Investor Awareness is a term exercised by public companies and similar bodies to delineate how substantially their investors know their investment market.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ahmad, Draz, and Yang (2018) investigated the factors that are authoritative on outward foreign direct investment. Data were collected by comparing four Association of Southeast Asian Nations countries against dominant Asian economies during 1981-2013. An econometric model using ordinary least squares was figured for every country to ascertain the attributes affecting

outward foreign direct investment. The outcomes of time series analysis revealed that exchange rates, income, and human capital affect the outward foreign direct investment of most of the countries in the sample. Moreover, among comparatively advanced and prevailing economies, openness information was the most authoritative attribute, whereas income levels and exchange rates were prevalent constituents in case of Association of Southeast Asian Nations economies.

Guiso and Jappelli (2005) explored the epitomes of financial awareness and authenticated lack of awareness of financial assets in the 1995 and 1998 Bank of Italy of Household Income and Wealth. The findings revealed a positive correlation between aware of stocks, mutual funds and investment accounts against education, household resources, long-term bank relations and placeholders for social interaction. The authors concluded that lack of financial awareness has important managerial implications towards empathizing the stockholding puzzle in forecasting stock market engagement costs.

Clemons (2010) examined the engrossment of firm by an external group, organization, or influential analyst towards depicting greater investor awareness which can contribute to firm's value and cost of capital. The paper hypothesized the fact that investors have limited awareness. The examination of announced monthly Center for Financial Research and Analysis research reports from 1998 through 2004 manifested that selective information materializing in Center for Financial Research and Analysis research reports has not been confiscated into a firm's stock price anterior to the compendium of the Center for Financial Research and Analysis research report.

Methodology of the Study

A questionnaire was adapted from previous literature to collect data from potential investors for analysis. The questionnaire will be made available to investors at the Lahore Stock Exchange. A total of 270 questionnaires were distributed, of which 245 were returned by respondents. The response rate from investors was 90.7%. Five of the questionnaires received were incomplete and 11 were completed by unrelated individuals, so these 16 questionnaires were rejected. Therefore, the

number of questionnaires used in the analysis was 229. The sampling technique used in this study was convenience sampling. Descriptive analysis and multiple regression analysis will be used to analyze the collected data. Table 1 shows the results of Cronbach's alpha used to test reliability. The overall reliability is 0.894. EFA is used to test the validity of a questionnaire. Items with factor loadings greater than 0.4 are considered to be of substantive importance. All items in the questionnaire have factor loadings greater than 0.4, except for one item with a factor loading of 0.38. However, all elements included in the questionnaire were taken from a valid questionnaire from a previous study, so this will not be changed here.

Hypotheses of the study:

This study tests the following hypotheses:

H1: Economic expectations of investor have positive influence on investment decision making behavior.

H2: Economic expectations of investor have positive influence on information search.

H3: Information search has positive impact on investment decision making behavior.

H4: Information search mediates the relationship between economic expectations and investment decision making behavior.

H5: Overconfidence bias has positive influence on investment decision making behavior.

Research Design

Descriptive Research is an empirical examination in social science researches that strategies the dimension of occasions as it remains at the time of study (Bickman & Rog, 1998; Elliott & Timulak, 2015; Miksza & Elpus, 2018; Thyer, 2010). Hence, descriptive research is picked out for this study.

Research Instrument

In this study, survey questionnaire is used as the research instrument to collect data from the main respondents and analyze the proposed research hypotheses. The survey questionnaire consists of the

following elements: Demographic factors investment pattern. Sources: Financial advice, word of mouth, trade press. Perceptions of individual investors: Benefits, myths, and risks. Psychological factors: Overestimations of oneself, herd behavior, optimism, fear of loss. Social factors: utilitarian influence and value expression. Economic factors: Information about overall company performance, price changes and profitability.

Financial literacy

Investment intention and investment decision validity Testing Modified and adapted research instruments are further subject to face and content validity. Face validity is conducted to measure the extent to which a research instrument is objectively considered when discussing the construct being evaluated (Kuada, 2012; Litwin & Fink, 1995; Wainer & Braun , 2013). Furthermore, content or logical validity is performed to measure the extent to which a research instrument represents the full panorama of a well-considered construct (Daniel & Sam, 2011). Additionally, a panel of six subject matter experts evaluates the robustness of the face and content.

Pilot Study & Reliability Test

Subsequent to the face content validity, a pilot study is carried on for the following causes:

- To examine the adequateness of the modified and adapted research instrument
- To evaluate the feasibility of the modified and adapted research instrument
- To excogitate a rules of etiquette of data collection process
- To manifest an efficacious sampling frame and technique for the research

The pilot study constituted a sub-sample of 60 respondents in Coimbatore. The data collected during pilot study are put forward to Cronbach's Alpha test to evaluate the internal consistency.

Information Source Variables

Construct	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Information Source</i>				
Financial Advice	FAISQ1	4.1658	0.78456	0.912
	FAISQ2	4.1576	0.82005	
	FAISQ3	4.3235	0.84999	
Word-of-Mouth Communication	WCISQ1	4.3005	0.95801	0.895
	WCISQ2	4.2365	1.01303	
	WCISQ3	4.2125	0.84871	
Specialized Press	SPISQ1	4.1084	0.94664	0.893
	SPISQ2	4.0033	1.12243	
	SPISQ3	4.1691	0.99965	

Source: Primary Data

The constructs, items, mean values, standard deviations, and Cronbach's Alpha values of Information Source sub-scales are presented in Table 5.3.1. The Cronbach's Alpha values of Information Source sub-scales Financial Advice, Word-of-Mouth Communication, and Specialized Press are 0.912, 0.895, and 0.893 respectively. Regarding the mean values, the higher mean values are observed for Financial Advice - FAISQ3 (M=4.3235), Word-of-Mouth Communication - WCISQ1 (M=4.3005), and Specialized Press - SPISQ3 (M=4.1691). The lower mean values are observed for Financial Advice - FAISQ2 (M=4.1576), Word-of-Mouth Communication - WCISQ3 (M=4.2125), and Specialized Press - SPISQ2 (M=4.0033). Considering the standard deviation values, the maximum deviations are noticed for Financial Advice - FAISQ3 (SD=0.84999), Word-

of-Mouth Communication - WCISQ2 (SD=1.01303), and Specialized Press - SPISQ2 (SD=1.12243).

Area of Study

The geographical area of this study refers to the selected metropolitan cities in India:

- a. Chennai
- b. Bangalore
- c. Hyderabad
- d. Mumbai

Period of Study

The duration of this research is three years from 2017 to 2020. In particular, the primary data collection is carried out for a period of one year from November 2018 to October 2019.

Sample Size

In India, there are 1839 financial services companies with 6,693,015 registered investors as per BSE India. The sample units considered for this present research are the share market investors registered in a leading financial services company in India which has more than 5000 employees. Considering the data provided by the financial services company, the total number of active share market investors counted to a total of 38,526. As requested by the institution, the identity of the leading financial services company and the investors are not disclosed, but are preserved confidential. The sample size of the study is decided using DeMorgan's table of sample size. The sample size of this study is determined as 654 applying DeMorgan's table of sample size at 99% confidence level and 5% margin of error (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

Sampling Technique

Stratified Random Sampling Techniques applied to make out the potential unbiased respondents into the sample. The sample size calculated for this study is 654 individual investors. Initially, the individual investors are classified into geographical strata: Chennai, Bangalore, Hyderabad, and Mumbai. Eventually, from the selected metropolitan cities in India, the individual investors are randomly selected. The procedure of stratification is demonstrated in the following.

Stratified Sampling Technique

METROPOLITAN CITY	POPULATION	STRATA
Chennai	10,896	185
Bangalore	8,891	151
Hyderabad	6,960	118
Mumbai	11,779	200
TOTAL	38,526	654

Consequently, the researcher prepared 654 questionnaires and distributed them to the respondents. By annihilating and brushing up double-barreled, equivocal, and misinforming statements, 609 entirely filled in questionnaires remained at 93.12% response rate.

Statistical Tools Used for Analysis

The primary data are methodically examined using the following techniques in IBM SPSS V24.0 and IBM AMOS Statistics V24.0 statistical software packages:

- (i) Frequency Distribution, Mean & Standard Deviation
- (ii) KMO and Bartlett's test of Sphericity
- (iii) Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test

- (iv) Confirmatory Factor Analysis
- (v) Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk Normality Test
- (vi) Analysis of Variance
- (vii) Karl Pearson's Correlation
- (viii) Multiple Linear Regression Analysis – Stepwise
- (ix) Mediating Effects – Path Analysis
- (x) Chi-Square Test

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with Maximum Likelihood Estimation

Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
1. Gender	Male	438	71.9
	Female	171	28.1
	Total	609	100.0
2. Age	24 yrs or under	74	12.2
	25 - 30 yrs	146	24.0
	31 - 40 yrs	173	28.4
	41 - 50 yrs	97	15.9
	51 yrs or older	119	19.5
	Total	609	100.0
3. Marital Status	Single	167	27.4
	Married	401	65.8
	Others	41	6.8
	Total	609	100.0
4. Education	High School or less	39	6.4
		348	57.1

	Bachelor's Degree	155	25.5
	Master's Degree	67	11.0
	Others	609	100.0
	Total		
5. Annual Income	2.5 lakhs or less	87	14.3
	2.6 to 5.0 lakhs	313	51.4
	5.1 to 10.0 lakhs	183	30.0
	10.1 lakhs or more	26	4.3
	Total	609	100.0
6. Employment	Salaried	237	38.9
	Professional	63	10.3
	Business	124	20.4
	Others	185	30.4
	Total	609	100.0

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
7. Family Life Cycle	Single Adult	141	23.2
	New Couple	79	13.0
	Family with Child /	173	28.4
	Children	81	13.2
	Family with Teenager	135	22.2
	Family in Later Life	609	100.0
	Total		
8. Earning Members	1 Member	185	30.4
	2 Members	291	47.8
	3 or More	133	21.8

	Members	609	100.0
	Total		

Source: Primary Data

Individual Investor Awareness Variables

Construct	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Individual Investor Awareness</i>				
Benefits	BEIAQ1	4.3268	0.79262	0.875
	BEIAQ2	4.3169	0.79040	
	BEIAQ3	4.2217	0.71987	
Myths	MYIAQ1	4.1970	0.98871	0.701
	MYIAQ2	4.0985	1.01962	
	MYIAQ3	3.8030	1.14158	
	MYIAQ4	4.0903	1.04506	
Risk	RIIAQ1	4.1724	0.90947	0.827
	RIIAQ2	4.2167	0.96090	

Source: Primary Data

The constructs, items, mean values, standard deviations, and Cronbach's Alpha values of Individual Investor Awareness sub-scales are presented in Table 5.4.1. The Cronbach's Alpha values of Individual Investor Awareness sub-scales Benefits, Myths, and Risk are 0.875, 0.701, and 0.827 respectively.

Regarding the mean values, the higher mean values are observed for Benefits - BEIAQ1 (M=4.3268), Myths - MYIAQ1 (M=4.1970), and Risk - RIIAQ2 (M=4.2167). The lower mean values are observed for Benefits - BEIAQ3 (M=4.2217), Myths - MYIAQ3 (M=3.8030), and Risk - RIIAQ1 (M=4.1724). Considering the standard deviation values, the maximum deviations are noticed for Benefits - BEIAQ1 (SD=0.79262), Myths - MYIAQ3 (SD=1.14158), and Risk - RIIAQ2 (SD=0.96090).

SUGGESTIONS

Referring to the analysis and major findings, following suggestions are proposed:

Information Source Log

Source of financial information acquired by investors is determined to be a crucial factor in determining the awareness of the investors. Hence, it is suggested that the investors can maintain a log of information sources to interpret their pattern.

Grandness of Financial Literacy

Financial literacy is a skillfulness that is invariably essential for an investor. It also benefits the investor throughout the investment process. It is suggested that investors require a primary knowledge about various investment options. Financial literacy can lead to acquire appropriate budgeting skills and enhance the individual to design better savings action plan.

Initiating Appropriate Investment Intention

Investment intention is based not only on the business idea but the relationship an investor shares with the company he or she is planning to invest in. It is suggested that the investor has to initiate the

investment intention towards diverse investment portfolio in order to yield better results. Apparently, the study also suggests that investment intention should not only be based on emotional motives but also be rationally well contemplated.

CONCLUSION AND RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The purpose of this study is to uncover the psychological, social, and economic factors that influence stock market investment intentions. The results of this study will be important for financial advisors and financial service providers in clarifying the role of investors' financial literacy when investing in the stock market. The results revealed that among the subscales of investor awareness, investment advantage was a factor that strongly influenced individual investors' intention to invest in the stock market. The results of this study will enable financial advisors to provide more useful advice to investors according to their needs.

This study supports the fact that investor awareness leads to a positive investment intention. One of the important contributions of this study from a practical perspective is that improving financial literacy remains an essential foundation for converting investment intentions into market investment decisions. The results also suggest that improved financial literacy toward investment opportunities enables better investment decisions. This is an authoritative guideline for policy makers to provide investors with appropriate investment options.

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